

Effect of search engine optimisation on reliable healthcare information online | Healthcare SEO

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1. Objective:

This short presentation introduces the ongoing research project Healthcare SEO, which explores the impact of search engine optimisation (SEO) techniques on the visibility and perceived usefulness of evidence-based healthcare information online. This project investigates whether integrating SEO measures can improve the accessibility and relevance of reliable information without compromising quality.

2. Background:

While there are strict quality standards for the development process of reliable health information itself (Deutsches Netzwerk Evidenzbasierte Medizin, 2015), evidence-based resources like patient guidelines often underperform in search engine results pages (SERPs), decreasing their potential usage by and visibility for patients (Meyer et al., 2024). This issue persists even though such content may meet Google's EEAT (Experience, Expertise, Authoritativeness, Trustworthiness) criteria for YMYL (Your Money or Your Life) content, for instance through trustworthy publishers and backlinks by high authority domains for health information. However, especially in the case of patient guidelines, structural and technical factors limit visibility: e.g. many are designed with print brochures in mind and therefore published as PDF files rather than optimized HTML pages. As a result, patient guidelines are often insufficiently indexed and may fail to match user search behavior. The project operates at the intersection of public health education and information science and responds to the current reliance of people using search engines when seeking health information.

3. Methods:

The project is divided into two main modules:

1. **Technical SEO for visibility:** Using existing patient guidelines on hypertension and back pain as case studies, primarily technical SEO measures are applied (e. g. optimisation of meta and structured data, URL structure, headlines and more). A systematic keyword research and analysis to assess user queries in search engines is conducted using the Query Sampler (Schultheiß et al., 2023) and commercial tools as developed by Sistrix (2025). The effect of this intervention is evaluated through a pre-post design with visibility metrics such as SERP rankings for pre-defined, relevant keywords, click-through rates, number of unique visitors and time-on-site.

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2. **Content SEO for usefulness:** Offline copies of the selected patient guidelines are adapted based on the keyword research above. The content is edited to contain (further) keyword-related information and respond to common queries and frequently asked questions. These edited versions of patient guidelines are evaluated for perceived relevance through A/B testing and qualitative focus group discussions with target users (patients). The tested assumption is that aligning content language and structure with the user search intent improves the perceived usefulness of the content.

4. Presentation:

This presentation will share first insights and challenges including methodological considerations for evaluating visibility and utility, and reflections on the relevance of SEO measures for reliable healthcare information online.

Information search habits on the internet have been changing fast in the past two years, driven by the increased use of Large Language Models (LLMs) as a new primary source of information. Studies suggest that the role of LLMs as a source of health information will become increasingly important in the near future (Rao et al., 2025). This session will therefore also open up the discussion on how the accessibility and readability of online content for the crawlers of answer engine machines such as LLMs may also be considered and facilitated in the development and publishing process of information.

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